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Dietary supplementation of a plant-based diet with hydrolyzed microalgae–grape marc extracts: effect on oxidative status, intestinal functionality and microbiota in *Sparus aurata* juveniles

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The expansion of aquaculture and the rising cost of fishmeal have driven research into fish gut health and the replacement of marine-derived ingredients with alternative protein sources, within sustainable strategies aligned with the Blue Transformation. In this sense, the objective of this study was to evaluate the effect of including a functional ingredient based on hydrolyzed microalgae and grape marc extracts in feeds with high proportion of plant protein sources on growth, muscle composition, oxidative status, intestinal microbiota, and digestive functionality in gilthead seabream juveniles (*Sparus aurata*). Three experimental diets were formulated, all isoproteic (47%) and isolipidic (18%), namely: CT (control diet - a diet mimicking the commercial aquafeeds used for this species based on 20% fishmeal); PP (a plant-based diet replacing 60% of fishmeal with hydrolyzed vegetable protein); and PP-GG (the same PP diet supplemented with 2% of the microalgal-grape marc based nutraceutical, *LB-Green*_{Grape}). Results indicated a trend for improved growth performance and FCR in fish fed the PP-GG diet compared to PP group, although differences were not statistically significant. The inclusion of plant protein ingredients reduced muscle protein content, however, supplementation with

microalgae and grape marc extract in the PP-GG diet partially mitigates this loss. Fishmeal replacement with vegetable proteins also affected lipid composition, with higher mono-unsaturated fatty acid content and increased poly-unsaturated fatty acid retention in PP and PP-GG groups. Additionally, PP diet posed an oxidative challenge, evidenced by higher lipid peroxidation, while this was significantly reduced in the PP-GG group, confirming the antioxidant effect of the nutraceutical ingredient. Digestive enzyme activities significantly increased in pancreatic enzymes of PP-GG group. Finally, although no significant differences in intestinal microbiota composition were observed, PP group showed increased bacterial diversity. In conclusion, dietary fortification with the nutraceutical based on microalgae and grape marc extracts improved growth, reduced oxidative damage, and enhanced digestive capacity in gilthead seabream juveniles, highlighting its potential as a nutritional strategy for sustainable aquaculture.

KEYWORDS

dietary fortification, functional ingredient, intestinal microbiota, intestine histology, oxidative status, proximate composition

Highlights

- Gilthead seabream juveniles fed the plant-based diet supplemented with hydrolyzed microalgae–grape marc extracts showed improved growth, reaching a 6% higher final body weight compared with the plant-protein diet.
- Muscle protein content increased by 8.5% in fish fed the plant-based diet supplemented with hydrolyzed microalgae–grape marc extracts, improving the fatty acid profile compared with the plant-protein diet.
- Fish fed the plant-based diet supplemented with hydrolyzed microalgae–grape marc extracts showed improved intestinal functionality and tissue oxidative status, with lipid peroxidation reduced by over 30% compared with the plant-protein diet.

1 Introduction

In recent years, research interest in fish gut health has increased markedly, particularly in a context where the rapid expansion of the aquaculture industry, together with the stagnation of capture fisheries, has contributed to a substantial rise in fishmeal price (Camacho-Rodríguez et al., 2024). Consequently, feeds traditionally based on marine-derived ingredients have been progressively replaced by diets formulated with alternative protein sources, especially those of terrestrial plant origin (Gajardo et al., 2017; Quagliardi et al., 2024). In parallel, the growth of the aquaculture sector is closely associated with the adoption technologies and practices grounded in responsible and sustainable approaches, consistent with Blue Transformation strategies, in which the development of healthy and environmentally sustainable food systems is a central objective (Quagliardi et al., 2024). Accordingly, the transition towards alternative protein sources aims not only to reduce reliance on finite marine resources but also to mitigate the environmental impacts associated with fish feed

production. However, the incorporation of plant-based ingredients into aquaculture diets introduces new challenges, including digestive disturbances, nutritional imbalances, and alterations in the intestinal microbiota of fish (Tacon and Metian, 2015). These effects are largely attributed to the presence of numerous antinutritional factors in plant-derived ingredients (Krogdahl et al., 2010; Gajardo et al., 2017; Bruce et al., 2018; Seibel et al., 2022), which can impair nutrient absorption and negatively affect gut health, potentially leading to reduced productive performance (Zuberi et al., 2024). Consequently, research focused on gut health and on the capacity of fish to adapt to these alternative ingredients is essential to support the sustainable and efficient growth of the aquaculture sector while safeguarding health and welfare of aquaculture species. Furthermore, as feed conversion into biomass is closely dependent on digestive system functionality, optimizing digestive processes represents a critical factor influencing animal welfare, as well as the economic viability and environmental sustainability of aquaculture production (Encarnaço, 2016). In response to these challenges, the concept of functional feed has gained increasing attention in aquaculture nutrition (Van Doan et al., 2023). This approach extent beyond the fulfilment of basic nutritional requirements by incorporating nutraceutical ingredients aimed at promoting not only efficient growth but also overall animal health, including enhanced resistance to diseases and stress (Encarnaço, 2016; Dawood et al., 2018; Van Doan et al., 2019; Ampofo and Abbey, 2022). Functional diets have emerged as a key strategy in modern aquaculture, contributing to the sustainability of the sector by fostering immune competence and fish welfare, which in turn is associated with improved productive and economic performance (Macusi et al., 2023; Onomu and Okuthe, 2024; Yang et al., 2024). In this context, grape marc extracts have emerged as a promising and sustainable source of nutraceuticals for aquafeeds (Quagliardi et al., 2024). These extracts are particularly rich in phytonutrients and phytochemicals, notably polyphenolic compounds, which are natural antioxidants that have been reported to exert beneficial effects on fish gut health (Dawood et al., 2022; Jiang et al., 2022). Bioactive compounds present in grape

extracts may help counteract some of the adverse effects associated with the dietary inclusion of plant feedstuffs by improving digestive function and nutrient absorption (Pulgar et al., 2021; Caponio et al., 2023; Quagliardi et al., 2024). In addition, polyphenols have been shown to positively modulate the intestinal microbiota, promoting the growth of beneficial bacterial populations and thereby supporting immune function in fish (Zhang et al., 2022). Collectively, these effects contribute to improved overall health status and enhanced resistance to disease and stress, which is particularly relevant under the increasingly demanding condition of modern aquaculture production.

In addition to grape-derived extracts, microalgae have gained increasing attention in recent decades as promising functional ingredient in aquaculture feeds. Microalgae constitute a rich source of primary metabolites, such as protein, essential fatty acids, vitamins, and minerals, and also contain a wide range of bioactive compounds, such as carotenoids, omega-3 fatty acids, and antioxidants, which have been associated with improvements in fish gut health and growth performance (Ampofo and Abbey, 2022; Quagliardi et al., 2024). In particular, the incorporation of microalgae as nutraceutical ingredients not only support fish health and welfare but may also contribute to the overall sustainability of the aquaculture sector. As organisms that can be cultivated under diverse conditions, including the use of wastewater and effluents, microalgae do not compete with terrestrial crops for resources such as freshwater or arable land (Rizwan et al., 2018). In this way, their use is aligned with the Blue Transformation objective by reducing reliance on finite resources and mitigating the environmental impacts associated with aquaculture production (Quagliardi et al., 2024).

Among the wide diversity of microalgal species available, certain species have attracted particular interest in aquaculture nutrition due to their complementary nutritional and functional characteristics. Freshwater genera such as *Arthrospira* and *Chlorella* are characterised by their high protein content and balanced amino acid profile, as well as by the presence of bioactive compounds with well recognised antioxidant and immunomodulatory properties (Thangsiri et al., 2024; Ćmiková et al., 2025). In turn, marine species including *Microchloropsis* sp. and *Isochrysis* sp. are especially valued for their richness in long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids, notably EPA and DHA, together with carotenoids and other antioxidant molecules (Bhattacharjya et al., 2021; Sáez et al., 2022). Previous studies have evaluated these microalgae, either individually or in combination, in different fish species, reporting improvements in growth performance, feed efficiency, digestive functionality and physiological status (Galafat et al., 2020; 2024; Perera et al., 2020; Sáez et al., 2022). The combination of marine and freshwater microalgal species therefore allows the integration of complementary nutritional profiles within a single functional ingredient, which may enhance its biological value and provides a rational basis for its evaluation in aquaculture diets.

Taking these considerations into account, the objective of this study was to evaluate the effects of including a functional ingredient based on hydrolysed microalgae-grape marc extracts in the diets of juvenile gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*). The assessment focused on growth, proximate composition, muscle fatty acid profile, antioxidant capacity, digestive functionality, and intestinal microbiota.

TABLE 1 Ingredients and proximate composition (% dry matter) of the experimental diets.

Ingredients	Experimental diets		
	CT	PP	PP-GG
Fishmeal LT94 ¹	20.00	8.00	8.00
Lysine ²	1.20	1.20	1.20
Methionine ³	0.50	0.80	0.80
Squid meal ⁴	2.00	2.00	2.00
CPSP90 ⁵	1.00	1.00	1.00
Krill meal ⁶	2.00	2.00	2.00
Wheat gluten ⁷	10.00	12.00	12.00
Soybean protein concentrate ⁸	22.00	29.20	29.20
Pea protein concentrate ⁹	7.50	10.60	10.60
Fish oil ¹⁰	9.00	9.00	9.00
Plant oils ¹¹	4.30	5.70	5.70
Soybean lecithin ¹²	1.00	1.00	1.00
Wheat meal ¹³	16.90	14.40	12.40
Monoammonium phosphate ¹⁴	0.50	1.00	1.00
Vitamin and mineral premix ¹⁵	2.00	2.00	2.00
Vitamin C ¹⁶	0.10	0.10	0.10
<i>LB-Green_{Grape}</i> ¹⁷	–	–	2.00
Crude protein	46.90	46.40	46.60
Crude lipid	18.20	17.90	18.10
Ash	6.90	5.80	5.80
Nfe ¹⁸	22.70	24.10	23.20
Moisture	5.40	5.80	6.30

CT, control (20% fishmeal-based) diet; PP, plant-based diet; PP-GG, plant-based diet supplemented with *LB-Green_{Grape}*. ¹69.4% crude protein, 12.3% crude lipid (Norsildemel, Bergen, Norway). ^{2,3}Lorca Nutrición Animal SA (Murcia, Spain). ^{4,5,6}purchased from Bacarel (UK). CPSP90 is enzymatically pre-digested fishmeal. ⁷78% crude proteins (Lorca Nutrición Animal SA, Murcia, Spain). ⁸Soycomil, 60% crude protein, 1.5% crude lipid (ADM, Poland). ⁹Pea protein concentrate, 85% crude protein, 1.5% crude lipid (Emilio Peña SA, Spain). ¹⁰AF117DHA (Afamsa, Spain). ¹¹Blend of soybean, rapeseed, and linseed (4:4:2) oils (Aceites el Niño, Spain). ¹²P700IP (Lecico, DE). ¹³Local providers (Almería, Spain). ¹⁴Lorca Nutrición Animal SA (Murcia, Spain). ¹⁵*LifeBioencapsulation* SL (Almería, Spain). Vitamins (mg/kg⁻¹): vitamin A (retinyl acetate), 2 000–000 UI; vitamin D3 (DL-cholecalciferol), 200–000 UI; vitamin E (Lutavit E50), 10–000 mg; vitamin K3 (menadione sodium bisulphite), 2–500 mg; vitamin B1 (thiamine hydrochloride), 3–000 mg; vitamin B2 (riboflavin), 3–000 mg; calcium pantothenate, 10–000 mg; nicotinic acid, 20–000 mg; vitamin B6 (pyridoxine hydrochloride), 2–000 mg; vitamin B9 (folic acid), 1–500 mg; vitamin B12 (cyanocobalamin), 10 mg; vitamin H (biotin), 300 mg; inositol, 50–000 mg; betaine (Betafin S1), 50–000 mg. Minerals (mg/kg⁻¹): Co (cobalt carbonate), 65 mg; Cu (cupric sulphate), 900 mg; Fe (iron sulphate), 600 mg; I (potassium iodide), 50 mg; Mn (manganese oxide), 960 mg; Se (sodium selenite), 1 mg; Zn (zinc sulphate) 750 mg; Ca (calcium carbonate), 18.6%; (186–000 mg); KCl, 2.41%; (24–100 mg); NaCl, 4.0% (40–000 mg). ¹⁶TECNOVIT, Spain. ¹⁷*LB-Green_{Grape}* is a fine dry powder composed of a freeze-dried extract from Albariño white grape marc combined with a blend of enzymatically hydrolyzed marine and freshwater microalgae (*Arthrospira* sp., *Chlorella* sp. and *Microchloropsis* sp.) containing 37.500 ppm of total polyphenols/kg⁻¹. This product has been developed within the NeoGiant project (Grant 101036768) by I-Grape S.L and LifeBioencapsulation S.L., Spin-offs from Universidad de Santiago de Compostela and Universidad de Almería, respectively. ¹⁸Carbohydrate content estimated by calculation as Nitrogen free extract = 100 - (% crude protein + % crude lipid + % ash).

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Experimental diets

Three experimental groups were set up in triplicate, depending on the diet provided. The isonitrogenous (47% on dry weight basis)

TABLE 2 Amino acid profile (g 100 g feed⁻¹) of the experimental diets.

Amino acids	CT	PP	PP-GG
EEA			
Arg	2.60	2.81	2.57
His	1.33	1.37	0.94
Ile	2.07	2.06	1.92
Leu	3.41	3.46	3.24
Lys	4.00	3.70	3.25
Met	1.30	1.42	1.28
Phe	2.73	2.84	2.37
Thr	1.76	1.83	1.69
Val	2.36	2.50	2.24
NEAA			
Ala	2.75	2.65	2.49
Asp	4.26	4.45	4.21
Cys	0.24	0.27	0.24
Glu	9.64	10.89	10.16
Gly	2.14	2.16	1.98
Pro	3.08	3.42	2.82
Ser	2.08	2.37	2.16
Tyr	1.75	1.89	1.65
Glu	9.64	10.89	10.16
EAA/NEAA	0.61	0.56	0.54

EEA, essential amino acids; NEAA, non-essential amino acids; CT, control (20% fishmeal-based) diet; PP, plant-based diet; PP-GG, plant-based diet supplemented with *LB-Green_{Grape}*.

and isolipidic diets (18% of dry weight basis) were formulated at the CEIMAR-Universidad de Almería facilities (Servicio de Piensos Experimentales, Almería, Spain): i) CT: control diet, similar to commercial diets, including 20% of fishmeal; ii) PP: experimental diet with a high replacement level of hydrolyzed plant proteins (60% replacement of fishmeal); iii) PP-GG: PP diet supplemented with 2% *LB-Green_{Grape}*, a functional ingredient based on a blend of enzymatically hydrolysed marine and freshwater microalgae, primarily *Arthrospira* sp., *Chlorella* sp., and *Microchloropsis* sp. (LifeBioencapsulation S.L., Almería, Spain; <https://lifebioencapsulation.com/index.php/productos/>) combined with Albariño grape marc extract (I-grape S.L. Santiago de Compostela, Spain; <https://i-grape.es/producto/extracto-de-uva-blanca-igrabe/>). The functional ingredient was developed by LifeBioencapsulation S.L. and I-grape S.L., spin-offs from the University of Almería and the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain), respectively. Briefly, for the enzymatic hydrolysis of plant feedstuffs, ingredients were suspended (100 g dry weight/L) in 50 mM sodium citrate buffer (pH 5.0) and incubated at 50 °C under continuous agitation for 24 h in presence of a blend of enzymes (xylanase 20–000 U g⁻¹; glucanase 30–000 U g⁻¹; cellulase 10–000 U g⁻¹, and protease 10–000 U g⁻¹) providing a 0.05 enzyme to algae ([E]/[S]) ratio as detailed in Vizcaino et al. (2024). The hydrolysis of microalgae was performed

TABLE 3 Fatty acid profiles of the experimental diets (% of total fatty acids).

Fatty acids	CT	PP	PP-GG
14:0	2.13	1.84	1.81
16:0	16.99	16.31	15.88
18:0	4.47	4.41	4.23
16:1n7	3.67	3.23	3.09
18:1n7	3.33	3.13	3.05
18:1n9	21.65	22.81	23.28
20:1n9	1.48	1.30	1.26
18:2n6	16.78	18.51	18.45
18:3n3	7.31	8.61	8.72
18:4n3	0.88	0.86	0.85
20:4n6	0.57	0.54	0.54
20:5n3, EPA	4.81	4.11	4.06
22:5n3	0.56	0.49	0.48
22:6n3, DHA	7.62	7.03	7.23
Other FA	7.74	6.81	7.05
ΣSFA	25.39	24.35	23.63
ΣMUFA	31.73	31.85	32.02
ΣPUFA	39.39	40.94	41.28
Σn-3	21.18	21.11	21.47
Σn-6	17.84	19.53	19.51
Σn-9	23.48	24.38	24.79
n3/n6	1.19	1.08	1.10
EPA/DHA	0.63	0.58	0.56

SFA, saturated fatty acid; MUFA, monounsaturated fatty acid; PUFA, polyunsaturated fatty acid; CT, control (20% fishmeal-based) diet; PP, plant-based diet; PP-GG, plant-based diet supplemented with *LB-Green_{Grape}*.

as detailed in Galafat et al. (2022). All the enzymatic pre-treatments were carried out by LifeBioencapsulation S.L. (Almería, Spain). The inclusion level of 2% was selected as an intermediate value, based on previous studies in which inclusion levels in the feed ranging from 1% to 5% were evaluated (Sáez et al., 2022; Galafat et al., 2026). For manufacturing experimental diets, feed ingredients and nutraceutical ingredient were mixed together, and then water was added to the mixture (up to 300 g kg⁻¹) to make up the homogeneous dough in a vertical mixer (Sammic BE-40, Sammic, Azpeitia, Spain). The dough was passed through a two-screw laboratory extruder (Evolum 25, Clextral, France) to obtain 2 and 3 mm-diameter pellets. The extruder barrel consisted of four sections and the temperature profile. In each segment (from the inlet to outlet) was 90 °C, 92 °C, 95 °C, and 105 °C, respectively. The feeds were dried (30 °C, 24 h) in a 12-m³ drying chamber with forced-air circulation (Airfrio, Almería, Spain) and cooled at ambient temperature. On the following day, a vacuum oil coating was applied using a Pegasus PG-10VC LAB vacuum coater (Dinnissen, The Netherlands). The feeds were then stored in sealed plastic bags at -20 °C until use. Ingredients, proximal composition, amino acid and fatty acid profiles of the

experimental diets are shown in Tables 1, 2 and 3. The polyphenol profile of the experimental diets is detailed in Supplementary Material, Supplementary Figure 1.

2.2 Feeding trial and sampling

Experimental procedures were performed following the guidelines for animal research of the Ethics and Animal Welfare Committee of the University of Cadiz, according to Spanish laws (law 32/2007 and RD 53/2013) and European Union legislation (2010/63/UE). Procedures were approved by the Ethical Committee from the Autonomous Andalusian Government (reference number 23/10/2019/176).

The experiment was carried out (September–December 2023) at the indoor facilities of the Servicios Centrales de Investigación en Cultivos Marinos (Central Services for Marine Culture Research, SCICM) of the University of Cadiz (CASEM, Puerto Real, Cádiz, Spain). After an initial acclimation period of 14 days, juveniles with 13.33 ± 0.16 g initial mean weight were randomly distributed in nine 400 L tanks (~ 1.6 kg m⁻³ initial stocking density, $n = 30$ fish per tank, $n = 90$ fish per experimental group) in an open flow-through system by controlling the inflow rate of each of the tanks, with eight water renewals daily. The animals were kept under stable conditions, with a temperature between 19–20 °C, oxygen saturation >85%, 37‰ salinity, and natural photoperiod (10L:14O; light period 8:30 h to 18:30 h). The experimental diets were administered twice daily (9:30 h and 15:30 h) to apparent satiety (*ad libitum*) six days a week for 84 days. The feeding test was conducted blindly, without reference to the composition of the diets, to eliminate any source of subjectivity in the feeding of the animals. Evolution in fish body mass was performed by biometric samplings every 3 weeks, and feed intake was recorded weekly for each experimental replicate to calculate growth performance parameters.

At the end of the experimental feeding period, a final sampling was conducted for all fish, and biometric parameters were analyzed. Twenty-four specimens per experimental diet (8 fish per tank) were randomly selected and deeply anesthetized with a lethal dose of 2-phenoxyethanol (1 mL L⁻¹ seawater). Before tissue collection, fish were killed by the cervical section. The entire intestine of 4 fish per tank (12 fish per experimental treatment) was collected for digestive enzyme analysis. Additionally, intestinal samples were taken from three fish per tank for analysis using light microscopy, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and transmission electron microscopy (TEM), and also to assess the intestinal microbiota. Another 4 fish per tank were randomly sampled. Liver, a sample of white muscle, and intestine from each fish were taken and immediately frozen in liquid nitrogen and kept at -80 °C until use. All samples were stored at -80 °C until biochemical analyses.

2.3 Growth performance

The following growth parameters were evaluated: (i) Specific growth rate (SGR) = $100 \times (\ln \text{ final body weight} - \ln \text{ initial body weight}) / \text{days}$ and (ii) Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR) = total feed intake on dry basis (g)/weight gain (g); (iii) Protein efficiency ratio (PER) = weight gain (g)/protein intake (g).

2.4 Proximal composition and fatty acid profile

The proximal analysis of the microalgae-grape based nutraceutical, experimental diets and muscle fish samples were determined following the AOAC (2000) procedures for dry matter and ash. Crude protein (N \times 6.25) was determined by elemental analysis (C: H: N) with a Fisons EA 1108 analyzer (Fisons Instruments, USA). Values were expressed as percentage of dry matter (% DM). Amino acids (AA) profile was performed using a Biochrom 30 + Series amino acid analyser (Biochrom vLtd, UK) according to the manufacturer's protocol. The amount of total lipids was determined following the procedure described by Folch et al. (1957). Fatty acid (FA) profiles of feeds and muscle samples were determined by gas chromatography (Agilent Technologies 6880 N, Santa Clara, CA, USA) following the method described by Rodríguez-Ruiz et al. (1998), using a modification of the direct transesterification method described by Lepage and Roy (1984) that requires no prior separation of the lipid fraction. For this, 9 fish per treatment were used.

2.5 Antioxidant activities

Samples of liver, white muscle, and intestine were homogenized in ice-cold 100 mM Tris–HCl buffer containing 0.1 mM EDTA and 0.1% (v/v) Triton X-100, pH 7.8, to a final concentration of 0.1, 0.2, and 0.2 g mL⁻¹, respectively. All procedures were performed on ice. Homogenates were centrifuged at 30,000 \times g for 30 min at 4 °C, and the resultant supernatants were kept in aliquots and stored at -80 °C for further analysis.

2.5.1 Enzyme assays

The enzyme assays were performed on a PowerWaveX microplate reader spectrophotometer (Bio-Tek Instrument, USA) at 25 °C. For each determination, samples were measured in triplicate in 96-well microplates (UV Star[®], Greiner Bio-One Germany). The assay conditions in a final volume of 0.2 mL were as follows (Morales et al., 2004).

Superoxide dismutase (SOD; EC 1.15.1.1), 50 mM potassium phosphate buffer (pH 7.8), 0.1 mM EDTA, 0.012 mM cytochrome C, 0.024 UI mL⁻¹ xanthine oxidase, and 0.1 mM xantine as substrate (McCord and Fridovich, 1969). Catalase (CAT; EC 1.11.1.6), 50 mM potassium phosphate buffer (pH 7.8), and 0.1 mM H₂O₂ as substrate (Aebi, 1984). Glutathione peroxidase (GPX; EC 1.11.1.9), 50 mM potassium phosphate buffer (pH 7.1), 3.6 mM GSH, 3.6mM sodium azide, 0.2 mM NADPH, 1 UI mL⁻¹ glutathione reductase, and 0.01 mM H₂O₂ as substrate (Flohé and Günzler, 1984). Glutathione reductase (GR; EC 1.6.4.2), 0.1 M sodium phosphate buffer (pH 7.5), 1 mM EDTA, 1.4 mM NADPH, and 0.3 mM GSSG as substrate (Carlberg and Mannervik, 1975). Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PDH; EC 1.1.1.49), 50 mM imidazole-HCl buffer (pH 7.4), 5 mM MgCl₂, 12 mM HCO₃Na, 2 mM NADP, and 1 mM glucose-6-phosphate as substrate (Löhr and Waller, 1974). Enzyme activity is expressed as units (CAT, and SOD) or milliunits (GPX, and GR) per mg of soluble protein (U or mU mg P⁻¹

¹). One unit of SOD activity was defined as the amount of enzyme necessary to produce a 50% inhibition of the ferricytochrome C reduction rate, registered at 550 nm. For the rest of enzymes analyzed, one unit of activity is defined as the amount of enzyme required to transform 1 μmol of substrate per minute under the above assay conditions. The molar extinction coefficients for NADH/NADPH, and H_2O_2 were ϵ_{340} : 6.22×10^3 , and ϵ_{240} : 39.58 M cm^{-1} , respectively.

2.5.2 Lipid peroxidation levels

As an index of lipid peroxidation, the concentration of thiobarbituric acid reacting substances (TBARS) was determined according to the method of Buege and Aust (1978). An aliquot of the supernatant from the homogenate (100 μL) was mixed with 500 μL of a previously prepared solution containing 15% (w/v) trichloroacetic acid (TCA), 0.375% (w/v) thiobarbituric acid (TBA), 80% (v/v) 0.25 N hydrochloric acid, and 0.01% (w/v) butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT). The mixture was heated to 100 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 15 min, cooled at room temperature, and then centrifuged at $1,500 \times g$ for 10 min. Absorbance in the supernatant was measured at 535 nm compared with blank. Concentration of TBARS was calculated from a calibration curve of malondialdehyde (MDA) and expressed as nanomoles of MDA per gram of tissue (nmol MDA g T^{-1}).

2.6 Intestinal digestive enzymes

Intestine samples were manually homogenized in distilled water at 4 $^\circ\text{C}$ to a final concentration of 0.5 g mL^{-1} . Supernatants were obtained after centrifugation ($13,000 \times g$, 12 min, 4 $^\circ\text{C}$) and stored at -20°C for further enzymatic analysis. Determination of trypsin and chymotrypsin was carried out using 0.5 mM BAPNA (N-benzoyl-DL-arginine-4-pnitroanilide) and 0.2 mM SAPNA (N-succinyl-(Ala)₂-Pro-Phe-pnitroanilide), respectively, in 50 mM Tris-HCl buffer, 10 mM CaCl_2 (pH 8.5), following the procedures described by Erlanger et al. (1961) and Del Mar et al. (1979), respectively. For these two enzymatic activities, a unit of enzyme activity (U) was defined as the amount of enzyme that releases 1 μmol of p-nitroanilide (pNA) per min, measured spectrophotometrically at 405 nm, considering an extinction coefficient of 8800 M cm^{-1} . The total alkaline protease activity was determined following the procedure described by Alarcón et al. (1998), using as substrate 5 g L^{-1} of casein in 50 mM Tris-HCl (pH 9.0). One unit of total protease activity was defined as the amount of enzyme that released 1 μg of tyrosine per min in the reaction mixture, considering an extinction coefficient for tyrosine of 4.42×10^{-5} M cm^{-1} , measured at 280 nm. Leucine-aminopeptidase was determined using 2 mM L-leucine-p-nitroanilide (LpNa) as substrate in 100 mM Tris-HCl buffer, pH 8.8, according to Pfeleiderer (1970), while alkaline phosphatase activity was determined following the protocol described by Bergmeyer (1974), using p-nitrophenyl phosphate in 1 M diethanolamine, 1 M MgCl_2 buffer, pH 9.5, as substrate. For leucine aminopeptidase activity, a unit of enzymatic activity (U) was

defined as the amount of enzyme that releases 1 μmol of p-nitroanilide (pNA) per min, measured by spectrophotometry at 405 nm, considering an extinction coefficient of 8800 M cm^{-1} , while for alkaline phosphatase it was defined as the amount of enzyme that releases 1 μg of nitrophenyl per min, considering a molar extinction coefficient of 17,800 M cm^{-1} for p-nitrophenol, measured spectrophotometrically at 405 nm. Data were expressed as unit of activity (U) per gram of tissue. In addition, intestinal proteases were visualized using substrate-SDS-PAGE gels. Intestinal extracts were mixed with sample buffer (1:1) and electrophoresis was performed according to Laemmli (1970) using 12% polyacrylamide (100 V per gel, 45 min, 4 $^\circ\text{C}$). Zymograms revealing intestinal proteases were carried out using the procedure described by Alarcón et al. (1998).

2.7 Intestine histology

Intestine samples were fixed for 24 h in phosphate-buffered formalin (4% v/v, pH 7.2), dehydrated and embedded in paraffin according to standard histological techniques. Samples were placed so that the anterior and posterior intestines were cut into 5 μm transversal sections following the axis of gut lumen. All the slides were stained with haematoxylin–eosin (H&E). The stained preparations were examined under light microscope (OLYMPUS IX51) equipped with a digital camera CC 12 (Olympus Soft Imaging Solutions GmbH, Muenster, Germany). The images were analyzed using the specific software ImageJ version 1.45 (National Institutes of Health Image software, Bethesda, MD). The length of folds, enterocyte height, lamina propria thickness and number of goblet cells per 100 μm mucosal fold were determined with the aim of assessing possible modifications of mucosal folds, according to the alterations generally described in fish fed diets containing some plant protein sources (Escaffre et al., 2007).

2.8 Ultrastructural study of the intestinal mucosa

At the end of the feeding trial, intestine samples were observed by transmission (TEM) and scanning (SEM) electron microscopy. The samples for TEM were fixed in 25 g L^{-1} of glutaraldehyde and 40 g L^{-1} of formaldehyde in phosphate buffer saline (PBS), pH 7.5 (4 h, 4 $^\circ\text{C}$). Subsequently, the intestine sections were washed with PBS for 20 min and post-fixation was carried out with 20 g L^{-1} of osmium tetroxide. By means of consecutive immersions in ethanol solutions with a gradient that varied between 50 and 100% (v/v), the samples were dehydrated. Once dehydrated, the samples were embedded in a 1:1 mixture of Epon resin and 100% ethanol (v/v) under continuous stirring, for 2 h, embedded in pure Epon resin and polymerized at 60 $^\circ\text{C}$. Finally, the ultra-thin sections were placed on a 700 Å copper mesh and stained with uranyl acetate and lead citrate. The observation of the mesh was carried out with a Zeiss 10C TEM at 100 Kv (Carl Zeiss, Spain). Samples for SEM analysis were fixed in 4% formaldehyde (v/v) in phosphate buffer, pH 7.2, for 24 h. After this time, samples were washed and dehydrated in ethanol and dried at a critical point with absolute ethanol as intermediate fluid and CO_2 as transition fluid, using a

critical point dryer CDP 030 (Leica Microsystems, Spain). After drying, samples were mounted on supports and fixed with graphite (PELCO Colloidal Graphite, Ted Pella INC., USA), plated with gold (SCD 005 Sputter Coater, Leica Microsystems) and examined under a scanning electron microscope (HITACHI model S-3500, Hitachi High-Technologies Corporation, Japan). Once SEM and TEM images were obtained, they were analyzed using the UTHSCSA ImageTool software (University of Texas Health Sciences Center, San Antonio, TX, USA). In TEM images, length (ML), diameter (MD), and number of *microvilli* μm^{-1} were measured (Vizcaino et al., 2014), while in SEM images, enterocytes apical area (EA) was measured. Finally, data obtained from TEM and SEM images were used to estimate total absorption surface per enterocyte (TAS) according to Vizcaino et al. (2014).

2.9 Intestinal microbiota

The total DNA was extracted from each sample ($n = 9$ per experimental group) according to the protocol based on saline precipitation by Martínez et al. (1998), with minor modifications (Tapia-Paniagua et al., 2019). DNA concentration and purity were quantified fluorometrically with QubitTM dsDNA HS Assay Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) and by spectrophotometric and electrophoretic methods to study the degree of purity, quality, and integrity of the DNA. Isolated DNA was stored at -20°C until further processing. Isolated DNA was stored at -20°C until it was sent to the Ultrasequencing Service of Novogene Europe (Cambridge, United Kingdom) for further processing and sequencing. 16S rRNA of samples was sequenced on the Illumina MiSeq platform (Illumina, San Diego, CA, USA) with 2×250 bp paired-end sequencing. The exact amount of DNA used for library preparation and PCR was determined by the sequencing service.

16S rRNA gene amplicon was sequenced on Illumina MiSeq platform (Illumina, San Diego, CA, USA) with 2×250 bp paired-end sequencing in the Ultrasequencing Service of Novogene Europe (Cambridge, United Kingdom). Sequencing was carried out using the primers 341F and 806R directed to the variable regions V3-V4 of the 16S rRNA gene (5' CCTAYGGGRBGCASCAG 3' and 5' GGACTACNNGGGTATCTAAT 3' respectively) (Klindworth et al., 2013; Thijs et al., 2017).

Sequencing primers were completely removed using cutadapt, and the quality of the raw reads was then assessed with FastQC (Andrews et al., 2010). Barcoding sequences were processed using R DADA2 library (Callahan et al., 2016). Briefly, forward and reverse reads were truncated with decreasing quality metrics while maintaining sequence overlap. Paired reads were assembled after error modelling and correction, creating amplicon sequence variants (ASVs). Chimeric ASVs were removed by reconstruction against more abundant parent ASVs. Taxonomy was assigned to representative sequence variants using SILVA release 138 database, where sequences were classified at 99% identity and trimmed to the amplified region. The microbiota sequencing data analyzed in this study are publicly available in the NCBI repository (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) under the BioProject accession number PRJNA1399374. The corresponding BioSample accession numbers range from SAMN54475965 to SAMN54475989.

Abundance of ASV of the intestinal microbiota was processed using phyloseq (McMurdie and Holmes, 2013) and vegan library (Oksanen, 2017) in R statistical package. The observed richness and Shannon and Simpson diversity indices were calculated to assess taxonomic diversity. Principal coordinates analysis (PCoA) was used to evaluate the Beta diversity obtained by both weighted and unweighted UniFrac analysis. A one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's *post hoc* test was employed to assess statistical differences in alpha diversity indices, and a PERMANOVA to evaluate significant differences in UniFrac distances (weighted and unweighted) between treatments.

ASVs with an abundance of fewer than 10 reads in at least 10% of samples were filtered out for taxonomy analyses. Taxonomic abundance tables were normalized by total count to obtain the relative abundance percentages of each analyzed taxon. The R library ggplot2 was used to represent the relative abundance at phylum and family levels, and differential abundance analysis of taxa was performed using a one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's *post hoc* test. The PICRUSt2 analysis was conducted to predict the functional content of the metagenome using 16S rRNA gene data. The metagenomic functional compositions of the samples were imputed based on the abundance of ASVs using PICRUSt2 version 2.5 with default parameter settings for phylogenetic placement (<https://github.com/picrust/picrust2/wiki>). Differences in predicted pathway counts by PICRUSt2, defined by MetaCyc identifiers, were evaluated using the analysis tool ALDEx2 (Gloor, 2015), as suggested in the PICRUSt2 website ([https://github.com/picrust/picrust2/wiki/PICRUSt2-Tutorial-\(v2.4.2\)](https://github.com/picrust/picrust2/wiki/PICRUSt2-Tutorial-(v2.4.2))). Briefly, the predicted pathway count table was split into pairs groups, and the 'aldex' command for pairwise analysis was executed. From the ALDEx2 tabular output, we applied three progressively stringent significance cutoffs (ALDEx2 "effect" parameter) of 0.5 to identify differentially abundant pathways. Effect size and volcano plots were constructed from the ALDEx2 output.

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2.10 Statistical analysis

Data were presented as mean \pm SD. The effects of the different dietary treatments were determined by one-way ANOVA, considering a significance level of 95% to indicate statistical difference ($P < 0.05$), followed by a generalized linear statistical model (GLM analysis). Significant differences were determined using Tukey's multiple comparison test. Data with nonparametric distribution were analysed using Kruskal-Wallis one-way analysis. Also, discriminant analysis (DA) was conducted in digestive enzyme activities and morphometrical analysis of TEM and SEM images. The estimation of the validity of the discriminant function was based on the significance of Wilk's Lambda and the percentage of correct assignments to a certain diet. All statistical analyses were performed with Statgraphics Plus 18.0 (Rockville, Maryland, USA) software.

3 Results

3.1 Growth performance

After 84 days of feeding, fish in the CT group exhibited higher growth performance, as reflected by significantly superior SGR and FCR, resulting in higher mean body weight values (Table 4). Fish fed the PP-GG diet showed a partial improvement in final body weight and FCR; however, no significant differences were observed in SGR for this group. Furthermore, no significant differences in PER were observed among treatments, and mortality was not recorded throughout the experimental period.

3.2 Proximal composition and fatty acid profile of muscle

Table 5 presents the proximate composition of muscle tissue in juvenile gilthead seabream fed the different experimental diets after 84 days of the feeding trial. Fish fed the PP diets exhibited a lower muscle protein content compared with those in the CT and PP-GG groups, whereas lipid content did not differ among dietary treatments.

The muscle fatty acid profile was influenced by dietary treatment (Table 6). Fish in the CT group showed higher saturated fatty acid (SFA) levels compared with those fed the PP and PP-GG diets. In contrast, the PP-GG group exhibited a higher monounsaturated fatty acid (MUFA) content than the CT group. Furthermore, fish-fed the PP and PP-GG diets displayed the highest polyunsaturated fatty acid (PUFA) levels, however, the contribution of eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) was lower than that observed in CT-fed fish.

3.3 Antioxidant enzymes and lipid peroxidation level

The results of antioxidant enzyme activities and lipid peroxidation levels in liver, white muscle, and intestine are presented in Tables 7, 8 and 9, respectively. Overall, fish fed the PP diet exhibited an enhanced antioxidant response in these tissues compared with those fish fed the CT diet; however, lipid peroxidation levels increased in white muscle and intestine, while a decrease was observed in the liver. In contrast, the PP-GG diet was

associated with a reduced antioxidant response across all three tissues, accompanied by lower lipid peroxidation levels than those recorded in both CT and PP-fed fish.

3.4 Analysis of intestinal digestive enzymes

Figure 1 summarizes the results obtained for the different digestive enzymes analyzed. Overall, all pancreatic digestive enzymes evaluated exhibited a similar response pattern, with the highest activities of trypsin, chymotrypsin, and total alkaline protease activity observed in the intestine of fish fed the diet supplemented with the functional ingredient *LB-Green_{Grape}* compared with the CT and PP treatments. Fish fed the CT and PP diets showed comparable trypsin and total alkaline protease activities, with no significant differences between these groups. However, fish fed the PP diet exhibited higher chymotrypsin activity than the CT group, although values remained lower than those observed in the PP-GG group. In addition, zymograms revealed a comparable alkaline protease pattern in fish fed the experimental diets relative to CT specimens (Figure 2). Regarding enzymes associated to intestinal mucosa (Figure 1), no differences were observed in alkaline phosphatase and leucine aminopeptidase activities among dietary treatments, with all groups displaying similar activity levels.

3.5 Intestinal histomorphology

The results of the histomorphometric analysis of the intestinal mucosa are summarized in Table 10. Fish fed the PP-GG diet exhibited the highest intestinal fold length compared with those observed in the CT and PP groups. In contrast, fish in the PP treatment showed the lowest values for total enterocyte height and muscular layer thickness, whereas these parameters being significantly higher in fish from the CT and PP-GG groups. *Lamina propria* thickness was markedly influenced by the dietary treatment, with the PP group showing the highest values for this parameter, significantly differing from those observed in the CT and PP-GG groups (Figure 3). Finally, fish fed the CT diet showed significantly higher number of goblet cells per 100 μm^{-1} , followed by those fed the PP diet, whereas fish fed PP-GG diet showed the lowest abundance of this cell type.

TABLE 4 Growth performance in gilthead seabream juveniles after 84 days of feeding experimental diets.

Parameters	CT	PP	PP-GG	P
Initial body weight (g)	13.32 ± 0.26	13.23 ± 0.04	13.45 ± 0.04	0.5790
Final body weight (g)	50.76 ± 2.65 ^b	43.68 ± 0.64 ^a	46.38 ± 1.28 ^{ab}	0.0194
SGR (%/day)	1.59 ± 0.04 ^b	1.42 ± 0.05 ^a	1.47 ± 0.03 ^a	0.0067
FCR	1.24 ± 0.07 ^a	1.43 ± 0.01 ^b	1.30 ± 0.05 ^{ab}	0.0490
PER	1.73 ± 0.17	1.51 ± 0.02	1.69 ± 0.05	0.0650

CT, control (20% fishmeal-based) diet; PP, plant-based diet; PP-GG, plant-based diet supplemented with *LB-Green_{Grape}*. Specific Growth Rate (SGR) = $(100 \times (\ln \text{ final body weight} - \ln \text{ initial body weight}) / \text{days})$. Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR) = total feed intake on dry basis (g)/weight gain (g). Protein efficiency ratio (PER) = weight gain/protein intake. Values are shown as the mean ± SD. Values in the same row with different lowercase letters indicate significant differences ($P < 0.05$).

TABLE 5 Proximate composition (g 100 g⁻¹ dry weight) in the muscle of gilthead seabream juveniles after 84 days of feeding experimental diets.

Parameters	CT	PP	PP-GG	P
Total protein	72.06 ± 2.76 ^b	66.73 ± 2.92 ^a	72.39 ± 2.28 ^b	0.0041
Total lipid	33.64 ± 3.85	36.47 ± 2.01	35.03 ± 3.51	0.3414
Ash	4.43 ± 0.11 ^a	4.69 ± 0.09 ^a	5.69 ± 0.38 ^b	0.0013

CT, control (20% fishmeal-based) diet; PP, plant-based diet; PP-GG, plant-based diet supplemented with *LB-Green_{Grape}*. Values are shown as the mean ± SD of triplicate determination (n = 3). Values in the same row with different lowercase letters indicate significant differences ($P < 0.05$).

TABLE 6 Muscle fatty acid profile (% of total fatty acids) in gilthead seabream juveniles after 84 days of feeding experimental diets.

Fatty acids	CT	PP	PP-GG	P
14:0	1.96 ± 0.08 ^b	1.72 ± 0.06 ^a	1.65 ± 0.04 ^a	0.0027
16:0	17.14 ± 0.32 ^b	15.83 ± 0.23 ^a	16.01 ± 0.20 ^a	0.0014
18:0	4.31 ± 0.17	4.37 ± 0.14	4.25 ± 0.08	0.5851
16:1n7	4.91 ± 0.10 ^b	4.47 ± 0.02 ^a	4.44 ± 0.07 ^a	0.0003
18:1n7	3.43 ± 0.08	3.23 ± 0.07	3.22 ± 0.13	0.0579
18:1n9	26.53 ± 0.43 ^a	27.86 ± 0.30 ^b	28.50 ± 0.40 ^b	0.0019
20:1n9	1.07 ± 0.04 ^b	0.90 ± 0.04 ^a	0.87 ± 0.05 ^a	0.0030
18:2n6	14.16 ± 0.36 ^a	15.72 ± 0.20 ^b	15.99 ± 0.25 ^b	0.0004
18:3n3	5.85 ± 0.14 ^a	6.50 ± 0.13 ^b	6.78 ± 0.10 ^c	0.0003
18:4n3	0.77 ± 0.02	0.78 ± 0.01	0.76 ± 0.02	0.4219
20:4n6	0.49 ± 0.02	0.46 ± 0.02	0.46 ± 0.01	0.1532
20:5n3, EPA	3.18 ± 0.11 ^b	2.77 ± 0.11 ^a	2.66 ± 0.05 ^a	0.0012
22:5n3	0.86 ± 0.05 ^b	0.75 ± 0.03 ^a	0.71 ± 0.03 ^a	0.0116
22:6n3, DHA	7.31 ± 0.18 ^b	6.86 ± 0.24 ^a	6.66 ± 0.13 ^a	0.0147
Other FA	3.87 ± 0.08 ^b	3.81 ± 0.03 ^b	3.66 ± 0.03 ^a	0.0060
ΣSFA	24.75 ± 0.44 ^b	23.36 ± 0.24 ^a	22.96 ± 0.20 ^a	0.0001
ΣMUFA	37.57 ± 0.23 ^a	37.94 ± 0.14 ^{ab}	38.49 ± 0.40 ^b	0.0195
ΣPUFA	33.64 ± 0.32 ^a	34.98 ± 0.46 ^b	35.11 ± 0.24 ^b	0.0039
Σn-3	18.03 ± 0.10	17.75 ± 0.34	17.59 ± 0.14	0.0608
Σn-6	15.47 ± 0.36 ^a	17.15 ± 0.14 ^b	17.42 ± 0.21 ^b	0.0002
Σn-9	27.92 ± 0.39 ^a	29.05 ± 0.26 ^b	29.62 ± 0.40 ^b	0.0031
n3/n6	1.17 ± 0.03 ^b	1.03 ± 0.02 ^a	1.00 ± 0.02 ^a	0.0003
EPA/DHA	0.43 ± 0.00	0.40 ± 0.01	0.40 ± 0.00	0.0608

CT, control (20% fishmeal-based) diet; PP, plant-based diet; PP-GG, plant-based diet supplemented with *LB-GreenGrape*. Values are shown as the mean ± SD of triplicate determination (n = 3). Values in the same row with different lowercase letters indicate significant differences (P < 0.05).

3.6 Ultrastructural study of the intestinal mucosa

The results obtained from the analysis of SEM and TEM images are presented in Table 11. The inclusion of the *LB-GreenGrape* in diets for gilthead seabream was associated with increased *microvilli* length and a larger apical area of enterocytes in the intestine

compared with those observed in the CT and PP groups. In contrast, *microvilli* diameter was significantly higher in fish fed the PP diet than in the other experimental groups. Despite these differences, no increase in total absorptive surface was detected, as similar values were observed across all dietary treatments (Figure 3).

3.7 Analysis of the intestinal microbiota

The alpha diversity indices of the intestinal microbiota of gilthead seabream juveniles were evaluated in response to the experimental diets (Table 12). Observed richness was significantly higher in the PP group compared to both the CT and PP-GG groups. In contrast, although the Shannon and Simpson indices showed a trend toward higher diversity in the PP group relative to the CT and PP-GG groups, these differences were not statistically significant.

Beta diversity was analyzed using PCoA based on UniFrac distances (weighted and unweighted) (Supplementary Figure 2). The plots revealed distinct clustering of microbial communities according to the dietary treatments; however, PERMANOVA analysis indicated no significant differences among groups.

Taxonomic analysis at the *phylum* level showed variations in the intestinal microbiota composition among the experimental groups, although no statistically significant differences were detected (Figure 4A). In the CT group, Proteobacteria (64.66%) and Firmicutes (22.20%) were the predominant phyla. A similar microbial composition was observed in the PP-GG group, with Proteobacteria representing 64.44% and Firmicutes 21.10% of the bacterial community. In contrast, the PP group exhibited a more heterogeneous profile, characterized by a lower relative abundance of Proteobacteria (46.63%) and a higher proportion of Firmicutes (34.07%), together with an increased representation of Actinobacteriota (7.59%).

At the family level, differences in microbial composition were observed among dietary groups, but no statistically significant differences were found (Figure 4B). In the CT group, the most abundant bacterial families were Rhodobacteraceae (11.84%), Vibrionaceae (9.06%), Cellvibrionaceae (8.31%), Pseudomonadaceae (7.40%), and Sphingomonadaceae (5.48%). The PP group exhibited a distinct composition, with Moraxellaceae (11.97%) and Cellvibrionaceae (11.54%) being the most prevalent, followed by Pseudomonadaceae (9.31%),

TABLE 7 Antioxidant enzymatic activities and lipid peroxidation level in the liver of gilthead seabream juveniles after 84 days of feeding experimental diets.

Parameters	CT	PP	PP-GG	P
SOD	173.60 ± 10.40 ^b	131.60 ± 13.50 ^a	135.80 ± 7.70 ^a	< 0.0001
CAT	144.00 ± 12.40 ^b	170.60 ± 10.00 ^c	122.40 ± 10.60 ^a	< 0.0001
GPX	81.70 ± 7.40 ^c	71.00 ± 5.50 ^b	58.80 ± 5.80 ^a	< 0.0001
GR	11.30 ± 0.80 ^b	10.10 ± 1.10 ^a	10.20 ± 0.90 ^a	0.0131
G6PDH	100.30 ± 10.10 ^c	73.70 ± 6.90 ^b	60.70 ± 6.20 ^a	< 0.0001
TBARS	20.30 ± 3.10 ^b	13.20 ± 2.30 ^a	12.70 ± 1.70 ^a	< 0.0001

CT, control (20% fishmeal-based) diet; PP, plant-based diet; PP-GG, plant-based diet supplemented with *LB-GreenGrape*. SOD, superoxide dismutase; CAT, catalase; GPX, glutathione peroxidase; GR, glutathione reductase; G6PDH, glucose 6-phosphate dehydrogenase; TBARS, thiobarbituric acid reacting substances. Enzyme activity is expressed in U (SOD, CAT) or mU (GPX, GR, G6PDH) mg P⁻¹. TBARS levels expressed in nmol g tissue⁻¹. Values are mean ± SD of triplicate determination (n = 3). Values in the same row with different lowercase letters indicate significant differences (P < 0.05).

TABLE 8 Antioxidant enzymatic activities and lipid peroxidation levels in white muscle of gilthead seabream juveniles after 84 days of feeding experimental diets.

Parameters	CT	PP	PP-GG	P
SOD	58.40 ± 6.30 ^c	45.30 ± 3.50 ^b	36.40 ± 3.30 ^a	< 0.0001
CAT	0.21 ± 0.07 ^a	0.30 ± 0.06 ^b	0.25 ± 0.02 ^b	0.0070
GPX	1.11 ± 0.11 ^b	1.34 ± 0.20 ^c	0.93 ± 0.11 ^a	< 0.0001
GR	0.29 ± 0.05	0.25 ± 0.03	0.28 ± 0.02	0.0972
G6DPH	1.48 ± 0.20 ^a	1.36 ± 0.10 ^a	1.78 ± 0.21 ^b	< 0.0001
TBARS	13.80 ± 2.60 ^b	15.30 ± 1.00 ^b	10.60 ± 2.00 ^a	0.0003

CT, control (20% fishmeal-based) diet; PP, plant-based diet; PP-GG, plant-based diet supplemented with *LB-Green_{Grape}*. SOD, superoxide dismutase; CAT, catalase; GPX, glutathione peroxidase; GR, glutathione reductase; G6PDH, glucose 6-phosphate dehydrogenase; TBARS, thiobarbituric acid reacting substances. Enzyme activity is expressed in U (SOD, CAT) or mU (GPX, GR, G6PDH) mg P⁻¹. TBARS levels expressed in nmol g tissue⁻¹. Values are mean ± SD of triplicate determination (n = 3). Values in the same row with different lowercase letters indicate significant differences (P < 0.05).

TABLE 9 Antioxidant enzymatic activities and lipid peroxidation levels in the intestine of gilthead seabream juveniles after 84 days of feeding experimental diets.

Parameters	CT	PP	PP-GG	P
SOD	314.80 ± 26.30 ^c	252.60 ± 22.80 ^b	220.40 ± 26.00 ^a	< 0.0001
CAT	63.50 ± 11.50 ^b	55.82 ± 9.70 ^b	45.80 ± 5.20 ^a	< 0.0001
GPX	14.20 ± 1.54 ^c	9.32 ± 1.65 ^b	7.25 ± 0.62 ^a	< 0.0001
GR	12.06 ± 1.90 ^b	8.41 ± 1.23 ^a	7.58 ± 0.96 ^a	< 0.0001
G6DPH	8.41 ± 1.11	7.64 ± 0.66	7.58 ± 0.76	0.0709
TBARS	63.00 ± 7.30 ^b	80.10 ± 12.80 ^b	54.00 ± 6.00 ^a	< 0.0001

CT, control (20% fishmeal-based) diet; PP, plant-based diet; PP-GG, plant-based diet supplemented with *LB-Green_{Grape}*. SOD, superoxide dismutase; CAT, catalase; GPX, glutathione peroxidase; GR, glutathione reductase; G6PDH, glucose 6-phosphate dehydrogenase; TBARS, thiobarbituric acid reacting substances. Enzyme activity is expressed in U (SOD, CAT) or mU (GPX, GR, G6PDH) mg P⁻¹. TBARS levels expressed in nmol g tissue⁻¹. Values are mean ± SD of triplicate determination (n = 3). Values in the same row with different lowercase letters indicate significant differences (P < 0.05).

Xanthomonadaceae (7.41%), and Vibrionaceae (6.43%). In the PP-GG group, Rhodobacteraceae remained one of the dominant families (9.93%), along with Moraxellaceae (7.45%), Lachnospiraceae (6.99%), Cellvibrionaceae (5.72%), and Pseudomonadaceae (5.56%).

Furthermore, although the composition of the abundant ASVs varied depending on the diet (Figure 4), no statistically significant differences in microbial functions were observed in fish fed the experimental diets (Supplementary Figure 3).

4 Discussion

The replacement of fishmeal with plant-based protein sources represents one of the most economically viable and environmentally sustainable strategies for aquafeed production

(Rodehutschord et al., 2022; Tomás et al., 2005; Drew et al., 2007; Gasco et al., 2020). However, the inclusion of high levels of plant-derived ingredients in fish diets poses significant challenges, as it can negatively affect growth performance, digestive functionality,

and overall fish welfare (Gatlin et al., 2007; Oliva-Teles et al., 2015; Chakraborty et al., 2019; Diwan et al., 2021). In this context, the incorporation of functional ingredients into plant-based diets has been proposed as a strategy to mitigate these adverse effects (Sarker et al., 2007; Abdel-Latif et al., 2022; Galafat et al., 2022). Previous studies conducted in *Sparus aurata* and other fish species have reported partial or substantial improvements in growth performance and somatic indices following the dietary inclusion of microalgae or grape-derived functional ingredients (Perera et al., 2020; Molina-Roque et al., 2022; 2025; García-Márquez et al., 2023b; Martínez-Antequera et al., 2024), as also it was evidenced in the present study. Nevertheless, although significant differences in FCR and PER were detected among the experimental groups, SGR was not fully enhanced by the inclusion of the *LB-GreenGrape* nutraceutical, as also observed Cerezuela et al. (2012); Pulido-Rodríguez et al. (2021) and García-Márquez et al. (2023a) using microalgae for dietary fortification. These findings may reflect transient or not fully established responses during a relatively short to medium-term feeding trial.

Muscle proximate composition is a key indicator of both muscle quality and nutritional value, and protein deposition in muscle tissue is closely linked to fish growth (Dumas et al., 2007; Ahmed et al., 2022). In the present study, a significant reduction in muscle protein content was observed in gilthead seabream fed the plant-based diet. Comparable results have been reported in *Scophthalmus maximus* (Xu et al., 2016), *Rhynchocypris lagowskii* (Zhu et al., 2021), and *Paralichthys olivaceus* (Shen et al., 2024) when fed soybean-based diets. This decrease in muscle protein observed in the PP diet could be related to imbalances in the profile of essential and non-essential amino acids. As shown in the data (Table 2), PP diet presents a slight increase in some individual amino acids compared to the control diet, but the EAA/NEAA ratio decreases from 0.61 in CT to 0.56 in PP, suggesting a lower relative availability of essential amino acids for protein synthesis (Peres and Oliva-Teles, 2006; Church et al., 2020).

Notably, this effect was reversed in the PP-GG group, which exhibited muscle protein content levels comparable to those of the CT group. The inclusion of microalgae and grape marc extract in the PP-GG diet may have counteracted the imbalances observed in the PP diet by providing additional essential amino acids, and bioactive compounds with antioxidant and immunomodulatory properties. These factors could enhance metabolic efficiency and reduce protein degradation, thereby helping to maintain muscle protein at levels comparable to those of the control group. In

TABLE 10 Effect of dietary treatments on histomorphology of intestine in juvenile gilthead seabream juveniles after 84 days of feeding experimental diets.

Parameters	CT	PP	PP-GG	P
Fold length (μm)	1070.24 \pm 232.43 ^a	1001.02 \pm 280.65 ^a	1175.22 \pm 230.27 ^b	< 0.0001
Total enterocyte height (μm)	66.66 \pm 13.21 ^b	53.93 \pm 13.27 ^a	63.40 \pm 11.94 ^b	< 0.0001
Lamina propria thickness (μm)	21.46 \pm 12.59 ^a	30.04 \pm 7.95 ^b	19.69 \pm 4.70 ^a	< 0.0001
Muscular layer (μm)	64.88 \pm 11.95 ^b	56.20 \pm 19.81 ^a	67.01 \pm 17.67 ^b	< 0.0001
Submucosa layer (μm)	37.92 \pm 10.85	37.29 \pm 10.37	39.57 \pm 17.82	0.4871
Goblet cells 100 μm^{-1}	9.88 \pm 1.11 ^c	8.42 \pm 1.27 ^b	6.20 \pm 0.93 ^a	< 0.0001

CT, control diet; PP, plant protein-based diet; PP-GG, PP diet supplemented with 2% of the functional ingredient *LB-GreenGrape*. Values are shown as the mean \pm SD of triplicate determination (n=3). Values in the same row with different lowercase letters indicate significant differences ($P < 0.05$).

addition, supplementation with microalgae has been shown to improve intestinal health and nutrient digestibility, which may translate into more efficient utilisation of dietary proteins (Galafat et al., 2020; Mota et al., 2023). In line with these results, dietary

supplementation with grape extract and grape seed proanthocyanidins has been shown to increase muscle protein content in rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*), common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*), and *Carassius auratus* (Kesbiç and Yigit, 2019;

TABLE 11 Microvillar morphology of the intestine tissue of gilthead seabream juveniles after 84 days of feeding experimental diets.

Parameters	CT	PP	PP-GG	P
Microvilli length (μm)	2.10 ± 0.39 ^a	2.08 ± 0.37 ^a	2.41 ± 0.24 ^b	< 0.0001
Microvilli diameter (μm)	0.09 ± 0.01 ^a	0.11 ± 0.01 ^b	0.09 ± 0.01 ^a	< 0.0001
Enterocyte area (μm ²)	24.91 ± 2.84 ^a	24.40 ± 4.13 ^a	28.98 ± 2.60 ^b	< 0.0001
Total absorption surface (μm ²)	41.28 ± 7.66	41.77 ± 7.40	40.52 ± 4.00	0.8859

CT, control diet; PP, plant protein-based diet; PP-GG, PP diet supplemented with 2% of the functional ingredient LB-GreenGrape. Values are shown as the mean ± SD of triplicate determination (n=3). Values in the same row with different lowercase letters indicate significant differences ($P < 0.05$).

TABLE 12 Alpha diversity indices in the intestine of gilthead seabream juveniles fed with the experimental diets.

Indexes	CT	PP	PP-GG	P
Observed	425.9 ± 144.2 ^b	818.7 ± 220.8 ^a	382.7 ± 223.1 ^b	0.0008
Shannon	4.78 ± 0.76	5.50 ± 1.09	4.62 ± 1.11	0.1927
Simpson	0.97 ± 0.02	0.99 ± 0.00	0.95 ± 0.03	0.0609

CT, control diet; PP, plant protein-based diet; PP-GG, PP diet supplemented with 2% of the functional ingredient LB-GreenGrape. Values are shown as the mean ± SD. Values in the same row with different lowercase letters indicate significant differences ($P < 0.05$).

FIGURE 4

Relative abundance (%) of the taxa with abundance higher than 1% at the phylum (A) and family (B) taxonomical categories in the intestine of gilthead seabream juveniles fed with the experimental diets. CT, control diet; PP, plant protein-based diet; PP-GG, PP diet supplemented with 2% of the functional ingredient *LB-Green_{Grape}*. NA, Not assigned.

Mohammadi et al., 2021; Jahanbakhshi et al., 2023). This improvement in fillet protein content may be related to enhanced dietary protein digestibility (Kesbiç and Yigit, 2019).

The replacement of fishmeal with plant-based ingredients was also reflected in the lipid composition of fish muscle. Although total lipid content was not affected by dietary treatment, differences were observed in the fatty acid profile. Higher SFA levels were detected in

the muscle of CT-fed fish, whereas MUFA were more abundant in the PP and PP-GG groups, particularly linoleic acid. This increase can be attributed to the high proportion of plant meals in these diets (Knutsen et al., 2019), as well as to the grape extract itself, which is a source of unsaturated fatty acids, such as oleic and linoleic acids (Beres et al., 2017). In addition, PUFA retention was higher in PP and PP-GG groups than in the CT group, however, EPA and DHA

levels did not increase, which was expected given the partial substitution of fishmeal with plant-based ingredients.

The inclusion of plant-based meals in the PP diet represented an oxidative challenge, as evidenced by the enhanced antioxidant response observed in the analyzed tissues, compared to those CT-fed fish. Despite this response, increased lipid peroxidation was detected only in the intestine, supporting the hypothesis that intestinal health may be compromised by high levels of plant material in the diet (Tacon and Metian, 2015), mainly due to the presence of antinutritional factors (Krogdahl et al., 2010; Gajardo et al., 2017). In contrast, fish fed the PP-GG diet showed reduced lipid peroxidation levels in both the intestine and white muscle, confirming the antioxidant role of the grape-derived functional ingredients (Dawood et al., 2022; Jiang et al., 2022). Dong et al. (2025) reported that dietary inclusion of catechins (catechin, epicatechin, or epicatechin gallate) at a level of 1 g kg⁻¹ improved the antioxidant capacity of *L. maculatus*. However, the concentration of bioactive compounds used in that study was approximately 66-fold higher than that provided by the PP-GG diet. These findings suggest that the protective antioxidant effect of may not be strictly dose-dependent, but rather more closely associated with the presence of specific polyphenolic compounds, even when supplied at relatively low dietary levels. Regarding white muscle, as previously reported, PUFA retention increased in both PP and PP-GG groups. Given the high susceptibility of PUFA to oxidative processes, an increase in lipid peroxidation could be expected in both dietary groups. However, this effect was observed only in the PP group, thus supporting the protective role of the grape extract against oxidative damage and its contribution to improved flesh quality in PP-GG-fed fish. Catechin, epicatechin, and epicatechin gallate are among the main polyphenols present in the PP-GG diet (Supplementary Figure 1). These compounds have been shown to activate the Nrf2 signaling pathway, which regulates the expression of antioxidant enzymes such as glutathione peroxidase (GPx) and catalase under conditions of oxidative stress (Zhou et al., 2019; Dong et al., 2025). Accordingly, the antioxidant effect observed in the present study following dietary supplementation with the nutraceutical may be attributed to the same mechanism, even at the relatively low dietary levels used. The analysis of digestive enzyme activities is a widely used tool to estimate digestive and absorptive capacity at the intestinal level and represents a reliable indicator of nutritional status and dietary adaptation, both of which are essential for evaluating the suitability of alternative ingredients for aquafeeds (Engrola et al., 2007; Gisbert et al., 2018; Darafsh et al., 2020). In the present study, two groups of enzymes were evaluated: i) pancreatic secretory enzymes, including trypsin, chymotrypsin, and total alkaline phosphatase, and ii) intestinal secretory enzymes, including leucine aminopeptidase and alkaline phosphatase. Overall, a significant increase in pancreatic enzyme activity was observed, particularly in fish fed the diet supplemented with the functional ingredient (PP-GG). These results may indicate an enhanced digestive capacity associated with the inclusion of functional ingredients (Vizcaino et al., 2014; Qiao et al., 2019). Similar results have been reported in tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) and hybrid sturgeon (*Acipenser baeri* Brandt ♀ × *A. schrenckii* Brandt ♂) when grape seed extracts were

included in the diet (Zhai et al., 2016; Xu et al., 2021). By contrast, Dong et al. (2025) reported decreased intestinal trypsin and lipase activities in *Lateolabrax maculatus* fed diets enriched with 1 g kg⁻¹ catechin, indicating that high doses of this polyphenol can interfere with protein and lipid digestion and absorption. Considering that the PP-GG diet contained less than 10 mg kg⁻¹ of polyphenols, it is evident that negative effects reported by those authors are associated only with high dietary doses or the use with purified polyphenols. Although grape seed extract was not used exclusively in the present study, it is noteworthy that studies employing whole grape extract remain limited, highlighting the need for further research in this area.

Despite the increased digestive enzyme activity observed in fish fed with the *LB-Green_{Grape}*-enriched diet, the associated changes in intestinal morphology did not result in an increased absorptive surface. This finding underscores the need for further investigation into the mechanisms that may constrain nutrient absorption. These results are consistent with previous studies suggesting that functional ingredients can improve specific aspects of gut health without necessarily leading to a generalized enhancement of feed conversion efficiency or growth performance (Dawood et al., 2022; Jiang et al., 2022).

The observed changes in the intestinal microbiota composition of gilthead seabream juveniles highlight the modulatory effects of dietary interventions, particularly those associated with plant protein inclusion and the potential restorative role of the functional ingredient. The significant increase in observed alpha diversity in the PP group compared with the CT and PP-GG groups suggests that the shift toward a plant-based diet led to a higher number of microbial taxa. This finding is consistent with previous studies indicating that plant-derived ingredients provide complex polysaccharides and fibers that may serve as substrates for a broader range of bacterial taxa (Williams et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2024; Guo et al., 2024). However, the absence of significant differences in Shannon and Simpson indices indicates that while the plant protein diet altered the number of microbial species, the overall evenness of bacterial distribution remained relatively stable across dietary treatments. In addition, beta diversity analysis did not reveal clustering patterns associated with dietary treatments, suggesting that diet did not markedly alter the overall structure of the intestinal microbiota under the experimental conditions tested.

Partial replacement of dietary protein sources was not associated with statistically significant differences in gut microbial composition. However, variations in bacterial abundance were observed. At the phylum level, the dominance of Proteobacteria and Firmicutes across all groups is consistent with previous reports on the intestinal microbiota of gilthead seabream (Kormas et al., 2014; Naya-Català et al., 2022; Ruiz et al., 2024). Although non-significant, the PP group exhibited a higher proportion of Firmicutes and an increased presence of Actinobacteriota. Certain species of the phylum Firmicutes have been associated with the digestion of complex polysaccharides in rainbow trout and grass carp (Ni et al., 2014; Pérez-Pascual et al., 2021). Additionally, some members of Actinobacteriota are known to produce butyrate (Parada-Venegas et al., 2019), a short-chain fatty acid with beneficial effects on fish, including *S. aurata* (Estensoro et al., 2016). In contrast, the microbial

composition of the PP-GG group was more closely resembled that of the CT group at the *phylum* level, supporting the hypothesis that supplementation with 2% Albariño white grape marc combined with a blend of enzymatically-hydrolyzed marine and freshwater microalgae may help restore a microbiota composition similar to that of fish fed a conventional diet.

At the family level, the PP diet tended to shift the microbial composition, increasing the relative abundance of Moraxellaceae, Cellvibrionaceae, and Pseudomonadaceae compared with the CT and PP-GG groups. Additionally, Xanthomonadaceae were detected exclusively in the PP group, a family previously identified as a predominant member of the intestinal microbiota in farmed fish (He et al., 2016; Puello et al., 2018). This family includes species reported as fish opportunistic pathogens such as *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* (Geng et al., 2010; Abraham et al., 2016), while other strains have been reported as plant-associated probiotics capable of degrading and reducing toxic compounds (Mukherjee and Roy, 2016; Zhang et al., 2017). Conversely, Rhodobacteraceae were detected in the CT and PP-GG groups but were absent in the PP group. Li et al. (2024) reported a negative correlation between *Rhodobacter* abundance and the levels of SGR and WGR in yellow catfish (*Pelteobagrus fulvidraco*); however, no such correlation was observed in the present study.

Despite the lack of statistically significant differences in microbial composition, predicted functional capabilities of the bacterial communities did not differ among dietary treatments. This finding suggests that, although dietary changes may influence microbiota composition, the overall metabolic functionality of the microbial community remains relatively stable. In this regard, previous studies have reported that *S. aurata* possesses a highly adaptable intestinal microbiota capable of responding efficiently to metabolic challenges induced by dietary modifications (Piazzon et al., 2020; Cerezo-Ortega et al., 2021).

In conclusion, partial replacement of fishmeal with hydrolyzed vegetable proteins in gilthead seabream diets yielded both beneficial and challenging outcomes. While improvements were observed in digestive enzyme activity and lipid composition, certain limitations related to flesh quality and intestinal health were associated. Supplementation with functional ingredients, such as hydrolyzed microalgae-grape marc extracts, enhance antioxidant protection and modulate the intestinal microbiota, indicating a restorative potential to counteract the adverse effects associated with plant-based protein diets. Nevertheless, further research is required to elucidate the underlying mechanisms involved and to evaluate the long-term effects of these dietary strategies on fish performance, health, and welfare.

Data availability statement

The datasets presented in this study can be found in online repositories. The names of the repository/repository and accession number(s) can be found below: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/PRJNA1399374>.

Ethics statement

The animal study was approved by Experimental procedures were performed following the guidelines for animal research of the Ethics and Animal Welfare Committee of the University of Cadiz, according to Spanish laws (law 32/2007 and RD 53/2013) and European Union legislation (2010/63/UE). Procedures were approved by the Ethical Committee from the Autonomous Andalusian Government (reference number 23/10/2019/176). The study was conducted in accordance with the local legislation and institutional requirements.

Author contributions

AG: Formal analysis, Data curation, Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Visualization, Conceptualization, Resources. IR: Formal analysis, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Data curation, Visualization. AM-G: Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Data curation. AC: Data curation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Conceptualization, Formal analysis. JG: Data curation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Methodology. IC: Visualization, Methodology, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Formal analysis. MR: Investigation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. Vd: Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Methodology. AV: Writing – review & editing, Resources. MS: Writing – review & editing, Resources. TM: Resources, Writing – review & editing. AEM: Data curation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Resources, Formal analysis. MC: Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Resources. ML: Writing – review & editing, Resources. JM: Investigation, Conceptualization, Visualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision, Resources, Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. FA: Resources, Funding acquisition, Writing – review & editing.

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Conflict of interest

Author FA was a member of Lifebioencapsulation SL (a spin-off of the University of Almería), but was not employed by the company.

The remaining authors declare that this work was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Generative AI statement

The author(s) declared that generative AI was not used in the creation of this manuscript.

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Supplementary material

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